

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

NANO-PERFUMES

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ABSTRACT

The combination of safe perfumes, natural fragrances and a convenient way of applying them, gives a significant place to innovation and the application of technologies using nanomaterials for the production of cosmetic products, the so-called nanocosmetics, of which perfumery is also a part. The wide range of products available and the satisfaction of growing consumer demands for fragrance provide an opportunity for the application of nanotechnology in the manufacture and use of perfumes. Nano-perfumes can be defined as perfumes based on nanotechnology or nanomaterials. The aim of this paper is to present the characterization and application of nanoparfumes as an assortment of those marketed by the cosmetic industry. In the study have been used the descriptive - analytical approach, the methods of comparison, analysis and synthesis.

Keywords: Nano technologies, Nano cosmetics, Nano-perfumes, Perfume market.

Introduction

A traditional perfume is a solution of aromatic compounds (e.g., aromatic essential oils, absolutes, fragrance compounds, fixatives) dissolved in selected solvents [32]. According to the *Whitepaper on: Nanotechnology & AI Application in Fragrance Sector* [35], perfumes are defined as products that impart a good odor to the product and the person on which/whom they are used. As consumers' expectations and awareness increase, their demands on perfumes are also increasing. For the modern consumer these include: multifunctional properties; durability, ease of use, affordability.

Perfumes usually consist of aromas and various oils that give a pleasant smell. The growing worldwide demand for cosmetic products is accelerating the development of the cosmetic industry. This in turn is expected to drive the growth of the perfumes market [25]. As reported by *Mordor Intelligence* [13], the fragrances and perfumes market size is estimated at USD 72.72 billion in 2025 and is expected to reach USD 105.27 billion by 2030, growing at a CAGR of 7.68% during the forecast period (2025-2030).

The perfume industry is constantly adapting to changing consumer preferences. Millennials and Generation Z have significant purchasing power, making them a key target group for numerous perfume brands. They, in turn, are embracing the various trends, innovating in the perfume application process, striving to seek sustainability, adopting eco-friendly practices from sustainable packaging to sourcing materials locally. A commitment to eco-friendly materials and zero-waste practices is also highlighted.

The continuous development of technology does not bypass the cosmetics industry. Combined with preferences and daily use, increased demand and the need to comply with new requirements on a global scale, the perfumery industry (part of the cosmetics industry) is characterised by a distinct development of assortment in line with innovation and consumer preferences. Nanotechnologies and their embodiment in cosmetics are coming to the fore. All this determines the **relevance and interest** of the author to the problem studied. The **aim** of this paper is to present the characterization and

application of nanoparfumes as an assortment of those marketed by the cosmetic industry. In the study have been used the **descriptive - analytical approach, the methods of comparison, analysis and synthesis**.

Modern trends in scents

According to *Cosmopolitan* [14], 2024 is the year of fragrance, with experts predicting some pretty unique fragrance trends for 2025 that will entertain people - from quirky scents to unique formats and surprising formulations. In 2025, the fragrance industry size is estimated to be \$57.38 billion. According to *Research Nester* [24], the fragrance market is booming as a result of the expansion of the cosmetics sector across the globe. Given the increase in the latest generation of consumers, the skincare sector will undoubtedly see a rapid rise, especially with the advent of social media. On the other hand, the factors believed to drive the growth of the fragrance market include changes in consumer preferences. The perfume sector relies heavily on customer satisfaction as market trends and customer tastes change under various factors including price, aroma, packaging, reviews, and recommendations from others. These are proving to be significant to a strong market position in the future.

Among the market growth drivers, various market and marketing researches [24];[25] indicate:

- **growing need for eco-friendly fragrances:** consumers are returning to perfumes created with more natural ingredients as they become more aware of how their choices can affect the environment. Customer needs and preferences for such fragrances are helping the perfume market to flourish and meet customer demands;

- **growing popularity of e-commerce:** the number of perfume purchases from e-commerce sites is increasing due to the advantages of this shopping method: convenience and easy ways to purchase perfumes. More than 770 million customers worldwide now buy their preferred colognes and perfumes through e-commerce sites;

- **the expanding influence of celebrity endorsements and social media:** celebrity endorsements foster a relationship between the brand and the customer and

can trigger a more favourable reaction and a greater propensity to purchase perfumes. Consumers are more likely to follow the advice of influencers as they often convey ideas that are more credible and engaging, thereby expanding demand in the perfume market. One of the most cited studies on the topic reveals that celebrity endorsement is associated with over 25% increase in sales and trust.

- **companies announce innovative fragrances to accelerate market development:** major industry manufacturers are introducing innovative contactless fragrance devices and AI-based solutions for regular fragrance consumers. These solutions include offering a personal aroma profile for individual users and offering a fragrance based on their preferences. This is thus accelerating the growth of the perfume industry. According to *FMI* [15], the demand for perfumes will increase at a steady pace due to the growing use of travel assortments - travel sprays and travel flacons. In addition, they point out that the industry has seen significant product innovation over the past few years, with the use of natural and renewable ingredients gaining in popularity. Analysis over a different time period shows:

- **short term (2023-2026):** younger consumers and millennials are becoming more inclined towards personalisation and are willing to experiment with new concepts and brands. The average ratio of younger population compared to other age groups is significantly higher. This is observed in China, Kenya and Brazil. These factors are expected to drive the market growth in the initial phase of the forecast period;

- **medium term (2026-2029):** defined by the introduction of new technologies such as contactless fragrance devices as well as artificial intelligence-based fragrance solutions. These technologies, which are currently in their infancy, are expected to gain widespread acceptance during this period. Technological innovations will help consumers to easily discover and use their preferred fragrances;

- **long-term (2029-2033):** the emergence of e-commerce as the dominant shopping channel will impact market growth. The unprecedented penetration of the Internet and the widespread popularity of online shopping could expand the global perfume market. Thus, it becomes easier for consumers to choose and purchase a perfume that suits their unique preferences.

Innovation in perfume packaging design is becoming a key element in the fragrance sector. Innovative packaging design allows perfume brands to stand out in retail and online markets. A distinctive bottle shape, cap design or packaging material can become synonymous with a brand, helping to build a strong and recognisable identity. Furthermore, with the growing awareness of environmental protection, there is a significant shift towards the use of sustainable materials in perfume packaging, such as the use of biodegradable, recycled or recyclable materials instead of traditional plastics [16]. In addition to the traditional spray, brands are innovating in the application process perfume by introducing powder puffs, solid formats, etc. [13].

For serving the prevailing trends, the role of nanotechnology is emerging. The combination of safe perfumes, natural fragrances and a convenient way of application gives a significant place to innovation and the

application of technologies using nanomaterials to produce cosmetic products, so-called nanocosmetics, of which perfumery is now also a part.

Nano technologies and cosmetics

Nanomaterials are materials that are characterised by nanometre dimensions in at least one of the three dimensions. At the same time, dimensions on the nanometre scale can refer both to material samples as a whole and to their structural elements [5]. In a dimensional nanoscale, nanomaterials can be classified as (1) zero—spheres and clusters; (2) one—multilayer covering; (3) two—tubes, fibers, and plaques; (4) three—particles and quantum dots. These nanomaterials have different physicochemical properties compared to conventional cosmetic materials: optical, electrical, thermal and magnetic properties, all of which alter the sensory properties - this is due to the size and coating thickness of the nanomaterial particles [22].

Nanotechnology is a key technology that leads to product innovation. It uses materials on an incredibly small scale that acquire new properties compared to their larger form. A review and study by the authors [9] concludes the areas of use of nanotechnology in cosmetics and skin care products: nanoemulsions, nanolossions, nanosomes, nanoencapsulated vitamins and ingredients, nanospheres, etc. For other authors, the main target areas of nanotechnology cosmetics are skin care, hair care and perfumery. Polysomes, gold nanoparticles, liposomes, dendrimers, etc. are also widely used nanomaterials in cosmetics. The main areas in which nanomaterials are used are skin care products such as anti-aging and anti-wrinkle creams, makeup products, hair care products such as hair conditioners and shine serums, perfumes, with the technology enabling long-lasting effects of perfumes [33].

A special feature of nanotechnology is that it is a process in which a new technology or product provides new capabilities and better solutions without replacing the previous technology or product, and thus gives new life to old, time-tested technologies [6]. Thus, nanotechnology is making inroads into the manufacture and application of various personal care and cosmetic products.

Nanocosmetics, reviewed by Telyak [4], presents the nanoforms used as: liposomes - still one of the most commonly used and preferred by consumers delivery systems of active ingredients; nanosomes - thanks to their size, they can penetrate into the deep layers of the epidermis, where their thin shell dissolves and the skin receives the substances it needs "from within"; nanocomplexes - contain biologically active substances, ground to nanosized, each of which is delivered in strictly defined quantities in strictly defined layers of the skin.

Other authors' conclusions [23] on nanocosmetics state that in a world where consumer assessment and trends towards cosmetic products are changing rapidly, skincare manufacturers need to embrace all the technological requirements and environmental and social aspects associated with the modern concept of health and beauty (i.e. biotechnology, biodiversity, robotics, artificial intelligence, big data, intelligent supply chain management and the Internet of Things). Thus, strategic management is required in the use of natural raw

materials for the production of innovative nanocosmetic lines, based on a successful biodiversity of the ingredients used and on sustainable and environmentally friendly processes. Either way, future innovative cosmetics, which are constantly in demand by the majority of consumers, can be created by recovering and using innovative and effective products and safe ingredients of natural origin. These ingredients should eventually be nanostructured to increase their effectiveness, and incorporated into carriers made of micro/nanoemulsions with low levels of emulsifiers and preservatives.

These views are complemented by other authors [21], who in a study look at innovative cosmetic delivery systems that have the potential to function as “next generation intelligent transmission systems”. They further demonstrate that nanotechnology can be used effectively to enhance product safety, efficacy, stability and aesthetic appearance, which will ultimately lead to greater consumer satisfaction. It is important to work with nanoproducts and produce them in a way that improves their value, supports consumer health and the environment.

Nano-perfumes – characteristics and perspectives

Perfumery (french: *parfumerie*, from Latin *per fumum* – “through the smell”) is a set of products used to scent something. The most popular types of perfumery are: perfume, eau de parfum, eau de toilette, cologne, deodorant and air freshener [2]. The word “parfumerie” refers to substances used for fumigation (“incense” scents). Nowadays, perfumes are products based on aromatic substances that have a pleasant smell and are used to scent the hair, body, clothes, as well as for refreshing and hygienic purposes [1]. Depending on their origin, perfumes can be classified as natural or synthetic. When the perfume raw material is of natural origin, derived from plants or animals, it is called an extract or essential oil. If it is not such an assortment, the term concentrate is more generic. These words are used to designate the concentrated liquid containing the volatile aromatic substances [10].

The main quality indicator of a perfume is its aroma. The authors [31] explain that aromas have a longer shelf life when encapsulated. The coating acts as a protective barrier, increasing molecular stability and facilitating delayed or controlled delivery techniques. Many consumer goods customize the release and delivery of flavors using encapsulation. Several delivery systems, such as microparticles, nanoparticles, and liposomes, are being explored for aroma delivery. In addition, the selected nanoformulations have a thorough understanding of several elements of Quality-by-Design principles, such as critical material identification, process parameters, and quality attributes. Due to their small size, nanoformulations enhance macroscale qualities such as texture, color, and aromatic properties of products during storage. These platforms can be explored and refined to efficiently deliver perfumes with a particular aroma.

Encapsulation is a very effective method of limiting the loss of aromas during use and maintaining their release. Encapsulation processes involve encapsulating one or a mixture of substances in a protective coating

material, commonly referred to as a wall or shell material, which serves as a functional barrier, protecting the base material from its surroundings and providing a diffusion barrier that prevents or retards the release of the active compound. The core material may subsequently be released under specifically controlled conditions or in response to external stimulations. The sizes of these capsules can vary depending on the preparation technique used, with capsule sizes typically ranging from nanocapsules (<1 μm) to microcapsules (1-1000 μm) [30]. Interfacial polymerization has been used to prepare polyurethane/urea microencapsulations of perfume for industrial application on textile substrate for the purpose of manufacturing men's suits or microencapsulated perfumes for textile application have been obtained [29]. The technique of nanoencapsulation of essential oils represents a new horizon for the future production of water-based and solvent-free perfumes [12].

Nanoencapsulation offers the use of nanoparticles coated with natural enzymes in the process of producing expensive perfume compounds, and without undesirable or harmful main effects [34]. Nanoencapsulation (nano-delivery systems) can also help improve the properties and performance (durability, stability) of substances such as fragrances that may be negatively affected by altered environmental conditions (light, air). The use of nanoencapsulation in fragrance products promotes a more efficient (sustained) and time-controlled release of aromas. This can be used in the production of longer lasting fragrance samples used for marketing purposes, in textile fashion and fashion accessories (e.g. embedding perfume in textiles, shoes and jewelry) and other materials such as ceramics and baby nappies. The release of fragrances can be controlled over time by stimuli such as diffusion, pressure sensitivity [33];[34].

It is the currently known applications of nanotechnology in the manufacture and application of perfumes that are primarily based on nanoencapsulation methods, which involve coating nanoparticles with various substances. A key point is the production of the aromatic (perfume) ingredients and the time-controlled and sustained release of the fragrances [34].

Nano-perfumes can be defined as *perfumes based on nanotechnology or nanomaterials*. The authors [33] say that nanotechnology can be widely used in the field of perfumes and fragrances. The use of nanotechnology can facilitate the production of purer and more natural perfume compounds. **Nanoparticles** are used for this purpose. Nanoparticles can be suspended in a gas, such as an aerosol (*nanoaerosol*), suspended in a liquid known as *nanocolloids* or *nanohydrosol*, or embedded in a source known as a *nanocomposite* particle [28];[33].

According to the author team [17], nano-perfumes refer to alcohol-free, fragrance-containing **nanoeulsion** perfumes. In their view, the technology could provide an alternative solution to the problem of low durability of fragrances by eliminating ethanol and reducing the number of surfactants, co-surfactants and solvents used in the formula. In addition, nano-perfumes, which incorporate perfume compositions without the inclu-

sion of ethanol, enable the development of safe, consumer-quality products for a wider range of consumers, including children, teenagers and individuals with sensitive skin.

This is supported by other authors [32], who describe the application of nanoemulsions as a potential form of perfumery products. According to them, the development of water-based perfumes in the form of stable nanoemulsions containing fragrance compositions (in the range of 5-15 %) stabilised by non-ionic surfactants makes it possible to create safe products for a wider group of users, including children, adolescents and people with sensitive skin. In the perfume industry and current trends, the development of ethanol-free perfume compositions is a major area of focus. In this regard, the use of nanoemulsions with characteristic

properties, such as small droplet size with large interfacial area, transparent or translucent appearance, low viscosity and high kinetic stability, make them an ideal carrier for fragrances in the perfume industry. They can be a great alternative to water-based, alcohol-free perfumes, and solve the problems of oxidation and low bioavailability of fragrances with other alcohol-free fragrance carriers such as pomades or gels. This has been practically illustrated by researchers who, as a result of the studies performed, have obtained stable oil-in-water (O/W) nanoemulsions that are compatible with selected aromatic compositions and contain no ethanol or other solvent [20].

There are different types of applications of nanotechnology used in the perfume industry, summarized in Table 1 [35]; [7]; [33].

Table 1

Application of nanomaterials and nanotechnologies in perfumes

Types of nano application	Short characteristics
<i>Liposomes</i>	to deliver aroma, botanicals and vitamins from anhydrous preparations such as antiperspirants, body sprays, deodorants, etc.
<i>Niosomes</i>	suitable for the delivery of both hydrophobic and hydrophilic compounds; increased stability of trapped compounds was observed.
<i>Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SLNs)</i>	instead of a liquid lipid by stabilizing with polymers or surfactants; presence of intrinsic properties such as nanoscale geometry, increased penetration through the skin, minimal toxicity.
<i>Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs)</i>	have numerous advantages, such as increased skin hydration due to the occlusive properties, and the small size ensures close contact with the skin surface, resulting in increased skin penetration.
<i>Nano-emulsions</i>	are widely used as a medium for controlled delivery of various cosmetic products such as deodorants, hair products, etc.
<i>Gold nanoparticles</i>	inert in nature, highly stable, biocompatible and non-cytotoxic in nature.
<i>Nanospheres</i>	the substances are trapped, dissolved or attached and protected from chemical and enzymatic effects as well as from the effects of other degradation factors.
<i>Dendrimers</i>	precise delivery and selectivity, provide controlled release from the inner core as well as attachment to the surface.
<i>Nanocapsules</i>	nanocapsules nanostructures are the main reason active substances are released under controlled conditions and prevent harmful effects at the point of delivery.
<i>Cubosomes</i>	advanced nanostructured particles have the ability to encapsulate hydrophilic, hydrophobic and amphiphilic substances.
<i>Nano-dispersions</i>	suitable for both lipophilic and hydrophilic delivery of substances; suitable for hydrophobic active substances.
<i>Carbon nanotubes</i>	suitable carrier; biosensors based on carbon nanotubes have shown better reproducibility, sensitivity, reliability and cost-effectiveness.

Source: adapted according to [7]; [33]; [35].

Liposomes are small spherical vesicles composed of phospholipid bilayers capable of encapsulating a variety of compounds, including water- and oil-soluble substances, which are one of the most commonly used storage and delivery techniques for many active ingredients and various compounds in biology, medicine, and cosmetics. With the increasing number of active cosmetic ingredients, the concomitant challenge is to effectively protect, transport and use these substances in a reasonable manner. Many cosmetic ingredients are ineffective both topically and systemically when applied to the skin, so changing the method of delivery and skin interaction of active ingredients is a crucial step toward improving their effectiveness. Liposomes

can improve the method of delivery of active ingredients to the skin, increase their stability and thus improve the efficacy of cosmetic products [18].

Niosomes are vesicles composed of nonionic surfactants, which is why they are called niosomes. In addition to nonionic surfactants, they also contain cholesterol and charged molecules. Niosomes are characterized by advantages such as increased stability at variable pH, low cost, longer shelf life and less toxicity, have greater potential for targeted delivery along with controlled and sustained release. Various types of natural products, enzymes, genes, proteins can be incorporated into niosomes [27].

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) are lipid oil droplets stabilized by a surfactant and solid at normothermia. They are prepared from purified triglycerides,

complex glyceride mixtures and waxes, and are more stable than liposomes. They are used in place of liquid lipid, being stabilized with polymers or surfactants. SNLs are well known in cosmetics due to the presence of intrinsic properties such as nanoscale geometry, increased penetration through the skin, minimal toxicity, site-dependent activity and higher bioavailability [7].

Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) are colloidal nanosized delivery systems that contain a lipid mixture consisting of solid and liquid lipids at their core. This lipid-based nanosystem is presented as a biocompatible, non-toxic and safe delivery system compared to polymeric or metallic nanoparticles. It is characterized by safety, stability and high loading capacity compared to other lipid-based nanocarriers [19].

Nanospheres are colloids that exist as a matrix. They are complex systems that are network structures with a central core of colloidal material. With the help of nanospheres, ingredients penetrate easily and deeply into cells and tissues through the skin, being protected from enzymatic and chemical degradation [33].

Dendrimers are three-dimensional spherical single-molecule micellar structures, branched (therefore increasing the absorption rate) and globular in shape. They are considered an ideal system for targeted delivery because they are very stable structures and, due to their polyvalency, are chemically stable. Furthermore, they are biocompatible, biodegradable and environmentally friendly [33].

Cubosomes are self-assembled advanced nanostructured particles that are submicron and discrete in nature. They have high thermal stability and are capable of maintaining moisture in the skin. They provide controlled targeted release of bioactive substances with different loading capacities. Internally, cubosomes have a high surface area and possess lipid biodegradability [7].

Gold and silver nanoparticles have found application as active ingredients in cosmetic products with biocidal action and antimicrobial properties [26]. Gold nanoparticles are formed when a non-metallic polymer binds to nanosized metallic gold. This uses a gold-sulfur bond. The advantages of nanogold are: high stability, chemical inertness, no photo bleaching, non-toxicity. Gold nanoparticles exist in various forms, such as gold nanosphere, gold nanorods, gold nanocubes or branched nanostructures [33]. The application of nanotechnology helps to reduce the cost of producing perfume ingredients while enabling the production of purer and completely natural perfume compounds. This can be achieved by using nanoparticles such as gold-palladium, which can replace the luxurious and potentially toxic reagents that aid the oxidation of aromatic primary alcohols to aldehydes, which is one of the key processes in perfume production. In this way, products with natural fragrances could be produced [33].

Nanocapsules are microscopic spheres that consist of a solid or liquid core in which cosmetic ingredients are contained within a cavity that is encased by a polymeric membrane of natural or synthetic origin. They encapsulate the fragrance ingredients, providing precise control over the release of aroma. In this way, the durability of the scent is extended, providing a dynamic olfactory experience [7].

Nanoemulsions are composed of tiny droplets of oil and water stabilized by an emulsifying agent, featuring particle sizes measured in the nanometer range. The result is a stable and transparent blend that enhances the solubility of the aromatic oil, providing a luxurious and lasting fragrance experience.

Summaries by the author team indicate that with nanoemulsions, it is possible to obtain formulations with much lower surfactant content (approximately 5%-10%), which allows maintaining adequate system stability and makes them safe for the human body. Also, it is not necessary to use cosurfactants, solvents and solubilizers to obtain stable, transparent and pure nanoemulsion systems as a carrier for aromas [20].

Nano-dispersions open the way for the use of aromas that could not be used before due to their insufficient chemical stability. The application of fragrances in the form of oil-in-water nanosystems protects them from the negative effects of oxidative factors. This is a good way to control the release of flavours, extend their shelf life and make aromas more durable (during processing, storage or use). Thanks to their structure and it is possible to obtain transparent and stable water-based perfumes that are safe, non-toxic, non-flammable, odorless and with very good skin tolerance. Water-based perfumes have advantages such as the environmentally friendly nature of water, non-flammable compositions and public acceptance. In addition, water is a much cheaper base than ethanol, providing cost savings in production [20].

Carbon nanotubes have a cylindrical shape and are assembled by winding one or several layers of graphene. There are two types: single-walled and multi-walled. They can be described as graphite sheets that are rolled into cylindrical shapes. These are a class of nanomaterials that have been studied for contaminant removal, desalination and water purification [8];[11];[33].

The authors' research [7] highlights that in order to enhance the use of nanotechnology in the cosmetic industry, **perspectives** such as: an in-depth study of the toxicity of TiO₂ and ZnO nanoparticles due to their full application in the cosmetic industry should be considered, as previous studies have shown mixed results. Liposomes and nanoemulsions should be used because of their stability as they are not removed from the skin even after washing and preserve the existing integrity of the lipid bilayers of the skin. The acceptability of microemulsions can be increased by using safer surfactants, as they do not alter the permeability of the membrane even after repeated use. Reliable and inexpensive triggers for controlled discharge of cosmetic molecules should be identified. There is a need to improve the ability of lipid-based nanoparticles, such as SLNs, NLCs, and nanocapsules, to transport substances. The transport, interaction and penetration of lipid nanoparticles into the stratum corneum of the skin need to be fully understood. The formulations of SLNs and NLCs, as well as the effect of wetting agents used for modifications, need to be further addressed. An in vivo study of cosmetic products containing nanoparticles should be performed. It can therefore be concluded that the use of nanotechnology in cosmetics is of great importance,

but the negative effects must be considered before using nanomaterials and any reservations associated with this advancing technology must be viewed with great caution and care.

The conclusions of other authors [34] on the issue point out that the main *problems* associated with the use of nanotechnology in perfumes, as well as in all personal care and cosmetic products, are related to potential hazards to human health and the environment. Nanoparticles can enter the human body in many different ways; nanoparticles from nano-based perfume products, for example, through the skin and inhalation. Due to their small size, nanoparticles are extremely mobile once they enter the body and there are concerns about the extent to which they can penetrate natural selective barriers in living organs. This is all due to the fact that nanosized particles tend to develop properties that cannot be explained entirely by their chemical nature, but by their size. There is also a scarcity of information on environmental studies conducted on the possible environmental impacts of nanoparticle dispersion during the life cycle of nano-based aromatic products. Nevertheless, in recent years, concerned public, non-governmental and even governmental bodies have increased their calls for more stringent regulatory systems that are more effective in controlling the production, risk assessment, processing and labelling of nanobased (cosmetic) products and that also apply the so-called precautionary principle.

Future research should focus on electronic noses. These are used to investigate the use of nanoparticles in fragrant products. Nanoparfumery ejectors are designed to mix nanoparticles with perfume and/or water particles and allow sterilization of air, absorption of unpleasant and release of pleasant odors [34]. Kuchmenko writes that electronic noses of the piezosorption type find wide application in the analysis of samples with complex and variable composition [3].

Conclusion

Nanotechnologies are a hallmark of development in any industry where they are applicable. They are synonymous with innovation and the future of that particular industry. In the face of dynamic trends and competition, nanomaterials have also found a place in the cosmetics industry - there is already talk of nanocosmetics. Perfumery products, are an integral part of everyone's daily life. The great assortment variety, which is characterized by the satisfaction of the constantly increasing consumer demands for fragrance, provides an opportunity for the application of nanotechnology also in the production and use of perfumes. The use of nanomaterials to ensure the durability and easy delivery of fragrances is a step forward, but should be carried out in full compliance with regulatory requirements to ensure the safety of the products manufactured.

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